

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF CARBON NANOMATERIALS BASED MACROSCOPIC ARCHITECTURES

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ABSTRACT

Carbon nanomaterials such as carbon nanotubes (CNTs) and graphene have drawn great attention over the past decade due to its extraordinary mechanical, electrical, thermal, and optical properties. In order to fully utilize the excellent mechanical and physical properties of individual carbon nanomaterials at a macroscopic level, it is desirable to fabricate various carbon nanomaterials based macroscopic architectures with controlled orientation and configurations. In this work, we focus on the preparation and mechanical properties of graphene based 2D paper materials and CNT based 3D sponge materials. Our results indicate: 1) graphene and/or its chemical derivate graphene oxide based films under low-amplitude dynamic tension display self-stiffening responses with as high as 200% increase in Young's modulus. We do parametric study based on a redefined Burgers' model to characterize the structure-property relations during the stiffening process. 2) Under compression, CNT sponges clearly exhibit super mechanical properties and stability: super-elasticity, high strength to weight ratio, thermo-mechanical stability in wide temperature range, negligible stress relaxation under high strain, excellent fatigue resistance after more than 3.5×10^6 cycles and frequency-invariant electro-mechanical stability. A thorough understanding of microstructural features and evolution of this CNT based structure to deformation was proposed to clarify their mechanical properties. Our works would be helpful for the design of various nanomaterials based macroscopic architectures with extraordinary mechanical behaviours.

1 INTRODUCTION

Nanostructured carbon materials such as carbon nanotubes and graphene have drawn great attention over the past decade due to its extraordinary mechanical, electrical, thermal, and optical properties. In order to fully utilize the excellent mechanical and physical properties of individual carbon materials at a macroscopic level, it is desirable to fabricate various carbon materials based macroscopic architectures with controlled orientation and configurations. So far, various forms of macroscale carbon materials based assemblies have been produced, such as 1D CNT/graphene based fiber, 2D CNT/graphene based films/sheets, and 3D aligned CNT array or CNT/graphene foams. These macroscopic architectures, depending on the manner in which they are assembled, display a variety of fascinating features that cannot be achieved using conventional materials.[1-5] In this work, we focus on the preparation and mechanical properties of graphene based 2D paper materials and CNT based 3D sponge materials.

Firstly, we design graphene and its chemical derivate (graphene oxide, GO) based macroscopic architectures with tuneable microstructure features. Our results indicate that these macroscopic materials under low-amplitude dynamic tension display self-stiffening responses with as high as 200%

increase in Young's modulus, which has not been previously reported for carbon nanostructures based macroscopic materials. We do parametric study based on a redefined Burgers' model to characterize the structure-property relations during the stiffening process. Our model incorporate mechanical behaviours of both GO sheets and their interaction for a full understanding of overall mechanical properties of graphene-based paper materials and further guide rational design of biomimetic self-stiffening functional materials.

Later, we fabricated CNT sponges with hierarchical structures through CVD method. Under compression, CNT sponges clearly exhibit super mechanical properties and stability: super-elasticity, high strength to weight ratio, thermo-mechanical stability in wide temperature range, negligible stress relaxation under high strain, excellent fatigue resistance after more than 3.5×10^6 cycles and frequency-invariant electro-mechanical stability. A thorough understanding of microstructural features (strong junctions between nanotubes) and evolution (completely elastic bending-buckling transition) of this CNT based structures to deformation was proposed to clarify their mechanical properties and nonlinear electromechanical coupling behaviour. Our work would guide for CNT-based cellular structure design and develop a basis for potential applications such as dampers, electrodes, electromechanical devices, synthetic biomaterials, and so on.

2 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Most synthetic materials, when subjected to dynamic stress, will undergo microstructural damage even though the strain is performed within the low strain level they could bear.[6] Instead, natural muscles are adaptive materials driven by a complex mechanism, and are capable of production of large strain with fast response time, moderate stress, high power density and long lifetime. Different from the way that biological tissues response to external stresses, the man-made materials generally response passively due to lack of structural complexity. Design and introduction of hierarchical architectures in synthetic materials becomes an alternative route to approach the goal.

Here, we report that the behavior of strain-induced mechanical stiffening happens to GO papers when subjected to low-amplitude (0.1%) dynamic tension. Figure 1a shows the self-strengthening response of GO paper when subjected to 10- μ m-amplitude dynamic tensile deformation. In general, most synthetic materials undergoing repeated tension or compression may fail due to fatigue even though the stress or strain applied is significantly lower than the level they could bear under monotonically loading conditions. Alternatively, GO paper displays an increasing storage modulus in response to repetitive loading. Moreover, there is no observable upper limit to this behavior after even 10 hours of continuous dynamic strain, indicating that there is potential for even greater improvement.

Figure 1: Evidence of dynamic self-stiffening in GO paper. The upper left inset is the digital picture of strip specimen. The specimen is dynamically stretched at 10- μ m amplitude, 1 Hz, 35 °C, a preload of 0.01 N using a DMA Q800 (lower right inset).

To elucidate the underlying self-stiffening mechanism of GO paper, it is essential to perform a parametric study based on the obtained self-stiffening curves. A redefined Burger's model was performed to quantitate stiffening behavior and further describe the GO sheets motion, which is

attributed to the straightening and reorientation of GO sheets. Here, we redefined the physical meanings of parameters in Burgers' model by redefining the physical meanings of the related parameters to quantitatively describe the increase in storage modulus during dynamic process. The storage modulus as a function of time could be described by the following equation (Equation 1):

$$E = E_I + E_R + E_L = E_I + E_r \left(1 - e^{-\frac{t}{\tau}}\right) + at \quad (1)$$

where the total storage modulus (E) consists of the initial modulus (E_I), the rapidly increased modulus (E_R) that depicts the modulus increase with a rapid rate which decays to zero exponentially in a short time, and the linearly increased modulus (E_L) that depicts the modulus increase almost linearly after E_R , which is related to the linear parameter (a) and dynamic procedure time (t). τ is the time taken to produce 63.2% of the E_R .

As stated earlier, E_R and E_L are time-dependent. To elucidate the contribution from straightening (mechanism i) and reorientation of the GO sheets (mechanism ii) in the increased modulus, the materials were then tested with several breaks during dynamic loads to ascertain whether the increased modulus would recover in the absence of dynamic loading (mechanism i) or not (mechanism ii). Figure 2 shows the self-stiffening curves (black) that consist of the rapidly increasing modulus (wine) and the linearly increasing modulus (olive) as a function of time. The numerical values of the mechanism caused recovered part during 2-min and 25-min breaks are quite close to the E_R in subsequent dynamic test after breaks, further implying that it is the stretching movement causing the rapidly increasing modulus.

Figure 2: 2-min break without any loading was performed during dynamic tests.

We also performed molecular dynamics (MD) simulations that elucidate these mechanisms at a microscopic level. We divide possible movements of GO sheets in response to dynamic stresses into two major mechanisms: (i) the first category of movements is attributed to the straightening of highly curved structure of GO sheets that enhances the tensile stiffness (Figure 3b). Importantly, the increased modulus can be gradually restored over time when unloading according to our MD simulation results. (ii) The second category of movements is related to the alignment of GO sheets, in which the misaligned GO sheets would reorient along the loading direction (Figure 3c). Thus, a mechanically stiffer sample is achieved due to better alignment of the two-dimensional lamellar structures. Once the removal of external loading, these aligned GO sheets would be difficult to return to the original state due to the cohesion between neighboring sheets and redistribution of water molecules in the interlayer gallery, and then there is permanent, or irreversible enhancement in the stiffness of specimens after repetitive tensile stresses.

Figure 3: (a) Microstructures of GO papers, where oxygen-rich groups are functionalized on graphene sheet, leading to corrugated morphologies, hydrophilic surfaces and an interfacial gallery open for various intersheet bonding types. (b) Stretching of highly curved GO sheet stacked in GO paper displays nonlinearly stiffening response. Results show that the mechanical response is reversible and increases rapidly with the strain measured from the curved state. The GO sheet can be restored to the curved state after removal of load. (c) Preferred alignment of GO sheets to the loading condition elevates the stiffness of the paper, which is an irreversible process due to the cohesion between neighboring GO sheets and redistributed water molecules in the interlayer gallery.

Earlier works have demonstrated that CNT-based sponge-like solids exhibit multi-functionality, good compressibility, ultra-light weight indeed, whereas the super mechanical stability is far from theoretical expectation. Herein, based on previous publications,[7,8] this unique biomimetic cancellous structure was achieved in macroscopic carbon nanotube monolithic sponges by chemical vapor deposition, in which individual nanotubes are randomly interconnected into 3D skeletons. The strong inter-tube bonding between neighboring nanotubes (junctions) guarantees the reversible deformation such as bending and buckling without structural collapse under compression. Systematic mechanical tests indicate that the resulting biomimetic CNT sponges could exhibit a combination of super-elasticity, fatigue resistance, thermo-mechanical stability and electro-mechanical stability. Compressive cyclic testing was conducted to assess the fatigue performance of CNT sponges at various applied strain levels for at least 1.8×10^6 cycles (Figure 5). In comparison, about 7% fatigue strain (shrinkage from the original length) was observed for PU materials, after 10 thousand cycles at set strains of 50%, and there is no observable ceiling to this fatigue behavior, which could be considered as fatigue failure or degradation. Note, however, that the fatigue performance of CNT sponges are remarkably stable and only 0.35% fatigue shrinkage could be measured after enduring millions of cycles, highlighting their structural robustness and fatigue resistance. By assuming 10% strain shrinkage to be a sign of fatigue failure, the life cycles of our CNT sponges could be estimated as more than 10^8 at 60% strain, in stark contrast to that of PU samples (10^4 at 50% strain), would be comparable to that of human skeletal muscle (10^9), showing their potential use in synthetic biomaterial fields.

Figure 4: Fatigue strain-cycles for the CNT and PU sponges. Insert: schematic of compressive cyclic testing. Tests are conducted at room temperature, a strain amplitude of 5%, a test frequency of 50 Hz, for the CNT sponges at different set strains of 10, 30, 50 and 60% and PU of 50% strain only. In PU materials about 7% fatigue strain was observed after 10 thousand cycles at set strains of 50%. The fatigue strain in CNT sponges after 1.8 million cycles at various strains of 10, 30, 50 and 60% is 0.14, 0.35, 0.34 and 0.58%, respectively. Note that even after 3.5 million cycles, the CNT sponges showed only 0.7% fatigue shrinkage.

To quantitatively understand and predict the structure–property relationships in CNT-based spongy materials, the unit cell model was taken out and shown in Figure 5a, in which the cell consists of four slender nanotube beams. Within our model, δ is the compressive displacement and may be expressed as: $\delta = \delta_{Bending} + \delta_{Buckling}$. The first contribution, due to bending of horizontal-layout nanotubes, is computed from the linear-elastic deflection of a nanotube beam loaded at its midpoint by a load P . When a uniaxial stress is initially applied to the sponge so that each cell node (inter-tube junction) transfers the force, the nanotubes itself bends and shows elastically linear load-displacement relationship (Figure 5 red line). Under increased strain, the second contribution, due to nonlinear but still elastic buckling of vertical-layout nanotubes gradually increased its proportion in total strain (Figure 5 blue line), and eventually total stress-strain response entered the non-linear region. Beyond a critical strain where bending and buckling strain contributed the total strain equally, a transient decrease in the load-strain slop (linear-plateau regime transition in stress-strain curve) can be observed, indicating the elastic structural evolution of the unit cell structure (Figure 5 black line). Meanwhile, at high strain level, the densification of the nanotube structure would result in increase of the modulus.

Figure 5: Microstructural evolution model. a) Schematic description of the unit cell model of the CNT sponge and the evolution in cell structure with strain. Inserts: SEM image of truss-like structure at 0% strain and schematic image of inter-tube junction (node). b) Evolution of total strain, bending strain and buckling strain while the carbon nanotube cell is experiencing increasing compressive load. The total strain is 20.3% when the buckling strain began to exceed the bending strain.

3 CONCLUSIONS

We have systematically investigated the mechanical behaviours of GO based paper materials and 3D CNT sponges. A thorough understanding of microstructural features and evolution of these nanostructured carbon material-based macroscopic architectures to deformation was proposed to clarify their mechanical properties. 1) The macroscopic GO papers indicated dynamic self-stiffening response with as high as 200% increase in modulus, which has not been previously reported for carbon nanostructures based macroscopic materials. On the basis of MD simulations and experimental results, we confirmed that stretching of curved structure of GO sheets and reorientation of GO sheets along the loading direction occurs during dynamic process. 2) Under mechanical compression, the CNT sponges clearly exhibit super mechanical properties and stability: super-elasticity, high strength to weight ratio, thermo-mechanical stability in wide temperature range, negligible stress relaxation under high strain, excellent fatigue resistance after more than 3.5×10^6 cycles and frequency-invariant electro-mechanical

stability. Our works would guide the design of various nanomaterials based macroscopic architectures with extraordinary mechanical behaviours and explore their potential application in biomimetic material fields.

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